

The Licchavi Suśrutasaṃhitā

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Historical background

The Suśruta Project: <http://sushrutaproject.org>

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- It has a colophon explicitly dating it to 878 CE and naming the monarch, King Mānadeva IV.

MS Kathmandu KL 699, colophon

MS Kathmandu Kaiser Library 699, f. 209v, courtesy the Nepal Research Centre.

Early discoveries

- The absence of the frame narrative concerning Dhanvantari.
 - Divodāsa original interlocutor.
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- Many simpler and shorter passages than the vulgate text. (E.g, absence of the Venomous Virgin narrative.)
- The incorporation of materials from the *Carakasamhitā* (forthcoming blog post).
- Many differences in materia medica and therapeutic interventions.

See project publications by Birch, Wujastyk, Klebanov, Parameswaran, et al. ([2021](#)), Birch, Wujastyk, Klebanov, Rimal, et al. ([2021](#)), The Suśruta Project ([2022](#)), and Wujastyk et al. ([in preparation](#)).

Conventions

- Scribal emendation of X to Y: X [Y]
- Scribal insertion of X: 'X'
- Editorial insertion of X: ⟨X⟩
- Unclear or uncertain: ~~~

Colophon lines 1 & 2

rājye[rājñi] śrīmānadeve pṛthusitayaśasi
prodyadinduprakāśe

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In the kingdom, when Śrī Mānadeva, having wide, bright fame,
shining like the rising moon,

Colophon lines 1 & 2

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In the kingdom, when Śrī Mānadeva, having wide, bright fame,
shining like the rising moon,

kāla puṇyārjjanasya saka'la'janamanohlādiramye vasante

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shining like the rising moon,

kāla puṇyārjjanasya saka'la'janamanohlādiramye vasante
of bestowing the merit of time when pleasing the minds of all
people, during spring

Colophon lines 3 & 4

varṣe caikottare 'smiṃs tritayaśatagate mādhave māsi śukle

Colophon lines 3 & 4

varṣe caikottare 'smiṃs tritayaśatagate mādhave māsi śukle
and in this expired year 301 in the bright half of the month of
Mādhava (April-May),

Colophon lines 3 & 4

varṣe caikottare 'smiṃs tritayaśatagate mādhave māsi śukle
and in this expired year 301 in the bright half of the month of
Mādhava (April-May),

saptamyāṃ puṣya-ṛkṣe da(śa)śata kiraṇavāsare siddhayoge

Colophon lines 3 & 4

varṣe caikottare 'smiṃs tritayaśatagate mādhave māsi śukle
and in this expired year 301 in the bright half of the month of
Mādhava (April-May),

saptamyāṃ puṣya-ṛkṣe da(śa)śata kiraṇavāsare siddhayoge
on the seventh day during the constellation of Puṣya, on the 110
Sunday, in the asterism called Siddha,

Colophon lines 5 & 6

utpattyādyambuvelākulavividharujagrahajujṣṭātiraudre

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utpattyādyambuvelākulavividharujagrahajūṣṭātiraudre

extremely violent being afflicted with various diseases and demons
that are churned up by the floods of water that are birth, etc. ...

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extremely violent being afflicted with various diseases and demons that are churned up by the floods of water that are birth, etc. ...

saṃsāre sāgare 'smiñ jagad idam akhilaṃ glāninam sampravikṣya

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utpattyādyambuvelākulavividharujagrahajajuṣṭātiraudre

extremely violent being afflicted with various diseases and demons
that are churned up by the floods of water that are birth, etc. ...

saṃsāre sāgare 'smiñ jagad idam akhilaṃ glāninam sampravikṣya
having perceived this whole world being sick in this ocean that is
samsara

Colophon lines 7 & 8

tasmāc chrīharṣacandro n̄niratiśayaghr̄ṇabhāvito
muktukāmaḥ

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tasmāc chrīharṣacandro nniratiśayaghrṇabhāvito
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therefore, Śrī Harṣacandra, moved by unsurpassed compassion
and the desire to liberate

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tasmāc chrīharṣacandro nniratiśayaghrṇabhāvito
moktukāmaḥ

therefore, Śrī Harṣacandra, moved by unsurpassed compassion
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prītyā cai° _____ °taṃ prālikhat suśrutākhyam

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tasmāc chrīharṣacandro nniratiśayaghrṇabhāvito
moktukāmaḥ

therefore, Śrī Harṣacandra, moved by unsurpassed compassion
and the desire to liberate

prītyā cai° _____ °taṃ prālikhat suśrutākhyam
joyfully wrote out the _____ called Suśruta

Colophon lines 9 & 10

श्रीगणेशदेवदेवकुलदुनी ग्वालकानिवसिनो
वैद्यवासुवर्माणः पुस्तकम्

śrīgaṇadevadevakuladūnī gvalakanivāsino
vaidyavasumarmaṇaḥ pustakam

Colophon lines 9 & 10

śrīgaṇadevadevakuladūnī gvalakanivāsino
vaidyavasumarmaṇaḥ pustakam

living in Deopatan in the temple of Śrī Śiva (Gaṇadeva), the book
belonging to Physician Vasuvarman

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idaṃ paṭhitvārtham avagamya sarvasattvānām upadeśaṃ
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idaṃ paṭhitvārtham avagamya sarvasattvānām upadeśaṃ
vidhātum

this, after reading, having understood the meaning, to spread the
teaching amongst all beings.

Colophon lines 11 & 12

pratipāditam, atas tad ādhikrayābhyāṃ taṃ gotrajena
kenacin na

Colophon lines 11 & 12

pratipāditam, atas tad ādhikrayābhyāṃ tañ gotrajena
kenacin na

had been presented. So it is not, for mortgage or sale by anyone in
that family

Colophon lines 11 & 12

pratipāditam, atas tad ādhikrayābhyāṃ tañ gotrajena
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kañcid dātavyam | yadā nopakriyate tadāsmān eva
pratyarpanīyam iti ||

Colophon lines 11 & 12

pratipāditam, atas tad ādhikrayābhyāṃ tañ gotrajena
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that family

kañcid dātavyam | yadā nopakriyate tadāsmān eva
pratyarpanīyam iti | |

to be given to anyone. When it is not in use, then it should be
rendered to me alone.

New light on the place of copying

- In colophon 9, we had *dūnī*. This is likely to be related to the classical Newari adverb *dunē*, that is listed in Joergensen's *Dictionary of the Classical Newari*:

dunē², *adv.* ch-g-yā ~ *in* (the interior of) C² 153; *dunēwo pinēwo inside and outside* H² 96^b.5. — *s.* the interior CW 1.38, the stomach (koṣṭha) AH 68^b.

Jørgensen 1936: 93. (Cf. Tamot et al. 2000: 227, Turner 1966–85: #6644 *drōṇī*?).

- *Gvalaka* is to be understood as the old name of Deopatan (Slusser 1982: 105, Michaels 2008: *chs.* 1, *passim*).

See also Regmi 1983: #CLXI: v. 1, 162–163; v. 2, 104, Petech 1984: 24, 29, 30, list no. 22, Dimitrov and Tamot 2007: 33.

The full text

In the kingdom, when Śrī Mānadeva, having wide, bright fame, shining like the rising moon, of bestowing the merit of time when pleasing the minds of all people, during spring and in this expired year 301 in the bright half of the month of Mādhava (April-May), on the seventh day during the constellation of Puṣya, on the 110 Sunday, in the asterism called Siddha, [in this saṃsāra that is] extremely violent, being afflicted with various diseases and demons that are churned up by the floods of water that are birth, etc. having perceived this whole world being sick in this ocean that is samsara therefore, Śrī Harṣacandra, moved by unsurpassed compassion and the desire to liberate joyfully wrote out the _____ called Suśruta, living in Deopatan in the temple of Śrī Śiva (Gaṇadeva), the book belonging to Physician Vasuvarman after reading, having understood its meaning, to spread the teaching amongst all beings. had been presented. So it is not to be given to anyone for mortgage or sale by anyone in that family. When it is not in use, then it should be rendered to me alone.

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